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Research Article

**RATE OF OCCURRENCE, MANAGEMENT AND DIAGNOSIS
OF ANENCEPHALY AMONG FEMALES****Dr Prof Muhammad Ali, Dr Saima Shams, Dr Warda Khan**
DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this study is to find out the rate of occurrence, management and diagnosis of the anencephaly.

Methodology: This was a prospective transverse research work conducted in a period of one year from June 2018 to May 2019 in Gynecology Department of DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan. Total 13 females with pregnancy having fetuses with the complications of Neural Tube Defect who got admission in the hospital were the part of this research work. We evaluated the establish diagnosis, various risk factors and rate of occurrence of anencephaly in this research work.

Results: The rate of incidence of the anencephaly was about 3.20 per one thousand deliveries and spina-bifida was two per thousand deliveries, we carried out the diagnosis of 100.0% anencephalic and 80.0% infants with the spina-bifida with the utilization of ultrasonography. The termination of the pregnancy carried out in sixty-two percent patients though normal delivery route of vagina. Total 12.0% female patients were present with diabetes. There was dominance of the female gender in the anencephalic fetuses as 61.5%.

Conclusion: Developed maternity cares, with the facilities for prenatal methods of diagnosis for the identification of the anencephaly and timely termination of abnormal fetuses can support to the prevention of this inherited problem with its related high rate of mortality. The supplementation of the folic acid prior from pregnancy and in the first three months of pregnancy can decrease the occurrence of this very complication.

KEYWORDS: Maternity, Vagina, Delivery, Termination, Prenatal, Anencephaly, Diabetes, Abnormal, Complication, Folic Acid, Occurrence, Fetus, Supplementation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Anencephaly is an abnormality of the congenital development which can be fatal with the involvement of the upper regions of the neural tube whose development starts 22nd to 25th day of the life of fetal. About sixty percent fetuses die before their birth and there will be no survivor more than fourteen days postnatal. The overall rate of prevalence of the anencephaly is only one per thousand child births. But there is a variation in its prevalence rate in different regions of the world. The rate of occurrence of this disease is very high in the northern parts of Ireland, Scotland and Wales. There can be multi-factors as etiological reason of this complication as the factors of environments and genes as well as there can be involvement of diet. There is demonstration of high protective impact of the supplementation of the folic acid on the recurring of the Neural Tube Defects. The acknowledges factors of risk for the Neural Tube Defects are the age of the mothers, weight of females, factor of race, the past background history of the last baby present with the Neural Tube Defects, not controllable high level of blood glucose and regular intake of the drugs as anti-epileptics. The most common related malformations with this very complication are cleft lip, cleft palate, spina bifida and the club foot. There is also description of the omphalocele. Antenatal identification depends on the failure of the demonstration of the cranial vault and the finding of the appearance like frog, large size of tongue, bulging eyes and very short size of neck. This identification can be made as soon as twelfth week with the help of ultrasound. The prenatal counseling of the couple present with infection about the pregnancy termination and handle the acknowledged factors of risk can be the steps for the prevention and administration of the

anencephaly. There is a decline in the rate of incidence of the neural tube defects because of the timely antenatal diagnosis and elective cessation of the pregnancies present with these complications. Periconceptual utilization of the supplementation of the folic acid decreases the initial occurrence and recurring of the neural tube defects. This very research work carried out to find out the rate of occurrence of the anencephaly and to assess the related and causative factors of risk for the propagation of this complication.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work carried out in a period of one year, in which two thousand four hundred and seventy-one deliveries took place in which thirteen babies were present with neural tube defect. The participants of this research work were the females with pregnancy who got admission through the outpatient's department or any in case of emergency in Gynecology Department of DHQ Teaching Hospital Dera Ghazi Khan with the identification of the anencephalic fetus depending on the medical assessment as well as ultrasonography. We gathered all information regarding the past history of the complication. We performed the investigation through laboratory tests and medical examination. We carried out the pregnancy termination after detail counselling and taking consent from the patients.

RESULTS:

Out of twenty-five hundred deliveries in the duration of this research work, we found only 13 neonates present with the neural tube defects. The rate of incidence of this complication was 5.260 per 1000 child births. Total 8 among thirteen fetuses (61.0%) were the anencephalic providing the birth incidence of 3.20 per 1000 child births (Table-1).

Table-I: Prevalence Of Neural Tube Defects/1000 birth

Congenital Malformation	No. of Cases	Prevalence/1000 births
Anencephaly	8.0	3.20
Spina bifida	5.0	2.00
Total NTDs (Neural Tube Defects)	13.0	5.20

The rate of occurrence of anencephaly reduced with the rise in the maternal age, being the minimum in the females having thirty-five years of age or more (7.80%) as elaborated in Table-2.

Table-II: Maternal Age And Neural Tube Defects (n= 13)

Maternal Age	No. of Cases	Prevalence/1000 births
less than 25	3.0	2.31
25 to 29	7.0	5.38
30 to 35	2.0	1.54
36 to 40	1.0	0.78
Total	13.0	5.26

The ultrasonography's sensitivity for the neural tube defects is highest for the anencephaly (100.0%) and its sensitivity is lowest for the spina bifida as 80.0%. Only one patient out of total thirteen with neural tube defects was normal routine antennal ultrasound as presented in Table-3.

Table-III: Antenatal Diagnosis Of Neural Tube Defects

Diagnosis	Total Cases	Detected by USG	Percentage
Neural Tube Defect	13.0	12.0	92.30
Anencephaly	8.0	8.0	100.00
Spina bifida	5.0	4.0	80.00

Out of total thirteen singletons present with NTD, there were total 61.0% (n: 8) pregnancies terminations. One patient got abortion spontaneously (8.0%). There were spontaneous deliveries from vagina in 3 cases (23.0%) at or near term and there was need of the CS (Cesarean Section) because of the major degree placenta Previa as presented Table-4.

Table - IV: Outcome Of Neural Tube Defects Regarding Mode Of Delivery

Outcome	No	Percent
Termination of Pregnancy	8.0	62.00
Spontaneous abortion	1.0	7.50
Spontaneous vaginal deliveries at or near term	3.0	23.00
Cesarean section	1.0	7.50

One female among eight present with the anencephalic neonates were also suffering from diabetes (12.50%). There was very poor folate intake. There were 8 females and 5 males among the affected neonates as presented in Table-5.

Table-V: Sex Distribution In Neural Tube Defects

Malformation	Total	Female		Male	
	No	No	Percent	No	Percent
Anencephaly	8.0	6.0	75.00	2.0	25.00
Spina bifida	5.0	2.0	40.00	3.0	60.00
Total NTDs	13.0	8.0	61.50	5.0	38.50

DISCUSSION:

In this current research work, the rate of occurrence of anencephaly was 3.20 per one thousand births while the reported occurrence of the anencephaly is one per thousand child births in the literature. Due to the multi-factors of etiology, there is variation in the rate of occurrence of the anencephaly in various regions of the world. In the countries which are developed, the rate of the occurrence of anencephaly and other defects of the neural tube are declining because of the counselling prenatally, antenatal screening and elective termination of the infected pregnancies at the initial period of the gestation.

Women in the period of their reproduction age managing the pregnancy obtain the prophylactic dose of 0.40 mg per day of folic acid and the females present with the past history of the babies with neural tube defect obtain the folic acid therapeutic dose 4.0 mg per day according to the recommendation of the public health service of U.S. The causes for the high incidence in our conditions may be attributed to the deficiency in the rate of prenatal counseling, absence of the use of the prophylactic folic, no availability of the timely diagnosis and termination of the pregnancies present with infections. In this current research work, the rate of occurrence of the anencephaly appeared to reduce with the enhancement in the age of females, which associates the maternal age with the particular occurrence of the neural tube defects in United Kingdom.

The exact cause of this occurrence is still not clear. A surplus of the female gender among fetuses present with the anencephaly was under observation which can be compared with the research work carried out by Kourey, but in opposition to the research work of the Eurocat, in which he found no difference. Antenatal detection for the occurrence of the anencephaly was 100.0% in comparison with the 80.0% diagnosis with the spina-bifida, as it needs the ultrasonography with high resolution as well as the professional skillfulness of sonographer. Regarding the termination of the pregnancy's mode having infection of neural tube defects (62.0%) underwent termination before complete term. This outcome of the research work has correlation with the research work conducted in United Kingdom on the defects of babies at birth time.

CONCLUSION:

Improvements in the maternity services, the utilization of the prenatal diagnostic methods and in time terminations of the affected pregnancies will support to decrease the rate of occurrence of this fatal abnormality of the congenital defects at the time of birth. The supplementation of the folic acid before pregnancy and in the duration of the three months of pregnancy can be much helpful for the reduction of the rate of occurrence of this very complication.

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